

LEARNING, TEACHING AND EDUCATING SYSTEMS FOR PUPILS IN UZBEKISTAN

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Abstract. *In our article, Teaching and learning process can be defined as a transformation process of knowledge from teachers to pupils. Based on the learning and teaching process, I wrote about the strategies of using foreign systems in Uzbekistan and the teaching process.*

Keywords: *Uzbekistan education system, teaching, learning, techniques, develop.*

СИСТЕМЫ ОБУЧЕНИЯ, ПРЕПОДАВАНИЯ И ВОСПИТАНИЯ ШКОЛЬНИКОВ В УЗБЕКИСТАНЕ

Аннотация. *В нашей статье процесс преподавания и обучения можно определить как процесс преобразования знаний от учителей к ученикам. Опираясь на процесс обучения и преподавания, я написал о стратегиях использования зарубежных систем в Узбекистане и процессе обучения.*

Ключевые слова: *система образования Узбекистана, преподавание, обучение, методики, развитие.*

INTRODUCTION

The speedy adjustments and extended complexity of today's international gift new demanding situations and positioned new needs on our schooling device. There has been normally a developing cognizance of the need to extrade and enhance the instruction of college students for efficient functioning withinside the constantly converting and extraordinarily disturbing environment. In confronting this mission it's miles important to bear in mind the complexity of the training device itself and the multitude of issues that need to be addressed. Clearly, no simple, unmarried uniform technique may be implemented with the expectancy that big upgrades of the gadget will occur. The approaches to teaching can be categorized according to major educational goals that affect teaching strategies. On one hand the goal of education is viewed as the transmission of knowledge by the teachers to the students. On the other hand the goal of education is viewed as facilitating students' autonomous learning and self expression. Indeed, any method for alternate have to take care of the numerous elements affecting the training gadget, the interactions of its parts, and the tricky interdependencies inside it and with its environment.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Teaching can be defined as engagement with learners to enable their understanding and application of knowledge, concepts and processes. It includes design, content selection, delivery, assessment and reflection. To teach is to engage students in learning; thus teaching consists of getting students involved in the active construction of knowledge. A teacher requires not only knowledge of subject matter, but knowledge of how students learn and how to transform them into active learners. Good teaching, then, requires a commitment to systematic understanding of learning. The aim of teaching is not only to transmit information, but also to transform students

from passive recipients of other people's knowledge into active constructors of their own and others' knowledge. The teacher cannot transform without the student's active participation, of course. Teaching is fundamentally about creating the pedagogical, social, and ethical conditions under which students agree to take charge of their own learning, individually and collectively.

RESULTS

Learning can be defined as the activity or process of gaining knowledge or skill by studying, practicing, being taught, or experiencing something (Merriam-Webster dictionary). Learning is about what students do, not about what we as teachers do. Among the maximum hard issues confronted through the training gadget are the ones related to coaching effectiveness. The present day instruction of instructors for unique age levels, precise issue matter, precise educational skills, etc., does now no longer think about sufficiently the complexity of things together with students' diverse characteristics. There is a robust want to teach instructors to conform preparation to the numerous scholar abilities, mastering styles, character trends.

DISCUSSION

In addition to the instruction of instructors to extra differentiated coaching, there can be extra divergent use of coaching sources. Worthwhile coaching may be finished with superb effects through men and women apart from the conventional school room instructors. For example, treasured coaching may be carried out via way of means of friends of various a long time and abilities. Also, parents, grandparents, and spouse and children should take part in and make a contribution productively to the coaching system. Furthermore, coaching may be more advantageous through volunteers, retirees, humans with diverse regions of information from the worlds of science, business, engineering, medicine, public service, entertainment, and others. Also, high-tech assets along with multimedia technology, laptop programs, telecommunication, the Internet, audio-visible techniques, and others can offer useful options. Student studying may be significantly enriched in addition through traveling - close to and far; interplay with humans of various cultures; one of a kind geographical regions; unique occupations, one of a kind approaches of life; extraordinary outlooks.

CONCLUSIONS

Undoubtedly, many opportunities exist that aren't frequently carried out despite the fact that they might make the coaching and getting to know method extra powerful and extra useful through presenting a whole lot of reports and opportunity techniques for version to students' characteristics.

REFERENCES

1. <https://necsi.edu/changes-in-the-teaching-and-learning-process-in-a-complex-education-system>
2. <https://www.teachthought.com/pedagogy/education-system-teaching-action-learning-process/>
3. <https://halshs.archives-ouvertes.fr/halshs-01712509/document>.
4. <https://brainuplab.com/overview-of-education-systems-and-teaching-methodologies/>